

Evaluation of the KKNi Curriculum Study Program for Indonesian Language and Literature Education

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Abstract:- Graduates of the PBSI Study Program S-1 are expected to be equivalent to level 6 of the KKNi. The description of learning outcomes in the KKNi contains four elements, namely elements of attitudes and values, elements of work ability, elements of scientific mastery, and elements of authority and responsibility, while in SN-Dikti the CPL formulation is listed in one of the standards, namely Graduate Competency Standards/SKL. In SN-Dikti, CPL consists of elements of attitude, general skills, special skills, and knowledge. The curriculum has been implemented in the 2020/2021 school year. The problem is that there are still many discrepancies between curriculum components, such as the distribution and types of courses. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the KKNi curriculum of the PBSI Unissula Study Program which focuses on 1) the objectives in the KKNi curriculum in the PBSI Unissula Study Program; 2) KKNi-based curriculum materials in the Unissula PBSI Study Program; 3) KKNi-based curriculum strategy at the Unissula PBSI Study Program; 4) KKNi-based curriculum organization in the Unissula PBSI Study Program; and 5) evaluation in the KKNi-based curriculum at the Unissula PBSI Study Program. The method used to evaluate the curriculum is an observation method that involves curriculum implementers and users, namely lecturers and students. In addition, a qualitative analysis was also carried out by comparing the components in the curriculum.

Keywords:- evaluation, curriculum, KKNi, indonesian language and literature education.

I. INTRODUCTION

The curriculum is the lifeblood of a learning program so that the curriculum requires dynamic design, implementation, and evaluation according to the times, science and technology needs and competencies needed by the community, as well as users of PT (Kemendikbud 2020) graduates. The development of science and technology took place very quickly, causing the SN-Dikti to change three times, namely Permenristekdikti No.49 of 2014 changed to Permenristekdikti No. 44 of 2015, and Permendikbud No. 3 of 2020. The issuance of Presidential Regulation Number 8 of 2012 concerning KKNi and Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education, encourages universities to adapt to these provisions. Likewise with the Curriculum of the Indonesian Language and Literature Education Study Program (PBSI), Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Sultan Agung Islamic University. The PBSI Study Program Graduate Program is

expected to be equivalent to level 6 of the KKNi. The description of learning outcomes in the KKNi contains four elements, namely elements of attitudes and values, elements of work ability, elements of mastery, and responsibilities and responsibilities, while in SN-Dikti the CPL formulation is listed in one of the standards, namely the Graduate Competency Standards/SKL. In SN-Dikti, CPL consists of attitudes, general skills, special skills, and knowledge. The KKNi-based curriculum of the Unissula PBSI Study Program has produced an KKNi-based curriculum structure. In the curriculum structure, there are several things that need to be reviewed, especially to adjust the courses to the expected learning achievement, as well as the distribution of the courses. Curriculum evaluation has a general purpose to obtain information about the implementation of the curriculum in schools and specifically to obtain answers to the completeness of curriculum components in schools, effectiveness of curriculum implementation, use of facilities, and level of learning outcomes (Hamalik, 2010). Based on these two objectives, the research problem is limited to evaluating the completeness of the curriculum in the PBSI study program. This is based on a) the KKNi-based curriculum of the PBSI Study Program has been implemented but is not yet optimal; b) there is already an agreement on learning outcomes by PBSI study programs throughout Indonesia but it is not optimal. For this reason, the effectiveness of the implementation, the use of supporting facilities, and the level of learning outcomes can be carried out.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many studies on the curriculum have been carried out, but research on the KKNi curriculum for the PBSI study program has never been done. Therefore, a literature review is needed to find out the novelty of this research. The following are some relevant studies, which can be used as a literature review. First, Solikhah's research in 2015 with the title "KKNi in Learning Outcomes-Based Curriculum". The result of Solikhah's research is that the qualifications framework is a government policy to determine the qualifications of the workforce and these qualifications need to be absorbed in the curriculum in schools and universities. KI has the same meaning as core competency, which is the bargaining power of how a program will succeed and be used in the community. To describe core competencies, it is necessary to formulate objectives, which are equivalent to SK and KD. In KI there are religious and social competencies. Religious competence is not included in the core competencies section for companies. Social and managerial competencies are clearly included and both are part of soft skills. Understanding of curriculum

development and design through needs analysis, KBK process, and formulation of learning outcomes and objectives would be able to instill the concept more steadily so that education actors are not "sold out" with new trends, and can immediately find their identity. Second, Siagian and Golda's research in 2018 with the title "Analysis of the Implementation of the KKNI-Based Curriculum at the State University of Medan". The results of Siagian and Golda's research are the curriculum evaluation model used in the form of the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) model. Based on the research that has been done, it appears that the implementation of the KKNI-based curriculum at Medan State University has been said to be good, although some aspects still need improvement such as lecturer readiness, completeness of facilities and infrastructure, availability of internship partners, and of course student readiness. Universities must continue to improve themselves so that graduates are able to compete with other graduates, both locally, nationally, and internationally. Third, Prabhandari and Primardiani's research in 2018 with the title "Evaluation of Curriculum Documents for the German Language Education Study Program, State University of Malang Refers to KKNI, SN-Dikti, and AUN-QA. The results of this study indicate that the formulation of the PSPBJ CP on the components of attitudes and values, knowledge, general and special skills is in accordance with the general description and description of qualification level 6 in the KKNI and the general attitude and skills formulation in SN-Dikti. In terms of documents, the PSPBJ curriculum is still not in accordance with AUN QA standards, especially in the Program Structure and Content criteria.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a curriculum evaluation model research with a mixed approach, namely qualitative and quantitative. A quantitative approach is used to calculate the positive/negative responses of curriculum implementers and users as well as the amount of agreement between curriculum implementers and users on the proposed improvements. A qualitative approach is used to map and analyze (strengths and weaknesses) of the KKNI-based curriculum of the Unissula PBSI Study Program, which then produces a set of instruments to be responded to by curriculum users.

A. Research Location and Time

This research was conducted at the PBSI Study Program, FKIP Unissula. The study was conducted for approximately 6 months. Research Data Source Sources of research data are the KKNI-based curriculum of the Unissula PBSI Study Program, implementers (lecturers) and users (students) of the KKNI-based curriculum of the Unissula PBSI Study Program, as well as lecture equipment. There are 6 lecturers who are the sources of research data. 4 permanent lecturers from PBSI Unissula study program, 2 non-permanent lecturers from PBSI Unissula study program. The students who were used as the source of this research data were 20 students of the 2018 and 2019 PBSI Unissula Study Program students.

B. Research Data

Research data on curriculum evaluation based on the KKNI of the Unissula PBSI Study Program in the form of a questionnaire consisting of five, namely, curriculum objectives, curriculum materials, curriculum strategies, curriculum organization, and evaluation in the KKNI-based curriculum of the Unissula PBSI Study Program.

C. Data Collection Methods and Techniques

The data collection of this research used the methods of documentation, observation, and interviews. The documentation method was carried out to obtain data on the curriculum structure based on the KKNI of the Unissula PBSI Study Program. The observation method was used to obtain data on learning achievement and intercomponent compatibility in the KKNI-based curriculum of the Unissula PBSI Study Program. The interview method was conducted by interviewing lecturers as curriculum implementers and students as curriculum users. In addition, interviews with stakeholders and alumni were also conducted regarding the relevance of the courses to the needs of the community. The interview method was used to obtain data about the implementation of the KKNI-based curriculum of the Unissula PBSI Study Program and the suitability of learning outcomes with the curriculum.

D. Data Collection Instruments

The data collection instrument consists of three things. First, the documentation guidelines in the form of evaluation criteria with fidelity criteria are compiled based on the KKNI-based curriculum of the Unissula PBSI Study Program. The criteria consist of 1) the competence of the study program; 2) curriculum structure that includes the distribution of courses in the elements of general and institutional curriculum competencies, curriculum fields of study. Second, the observation sheet is used as a guide in observing the conformity between components in the curriculum. Third, a list of interview questions used to obtain data on curriculum implementation. Data analysis Methods and Techniques of Data Analysis In accordance with the observation evaluation model used, the data analysis of curriculum evaluation research based on the KKNI of the PBSI Unissula 20 Study Program used contingency and congruence analysis. Contingency analysis consists of logical contingency and empirical contingency. Contingency is the result of the evaluator's consideration of the logical and empirical linkages between antecedents, transactions, and outcomes. Congruence is the evaluator's consideration of what is planned in the KKNI-based curriculum of the PBSI Unissula Study Program and the results of implementing the KKNI-based curriculum of the Unissula PBSI Study Program. The analysis produces items that need to be evaluated in the curriculum which is then presented in the form of a questionnaire to get responses from curriculum users. In addition, simple statistical analysis is used to determine the average response of curriculum users. The statistical analysis aims to produce an assessment of the KKNI-based curriculum of the Unissula PBSI Study Program, whether the curriculum is good or not. The formula used for the analysis is as follows.

User value (lecturer)

$\frac{\text{The score obtained} = \text{the value of each curriculum component}}{6}$

User value (student)

$\frac{\text{The score obtained} = \text{the value of each curriculum component}}{20}$
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E. Instruments In Data Analysis

Used instruments in the form of contingency and congruence sheets which are presented in the form of tables. The aim is to make it easier for the evaluator to analyze whether there is a relationship and suitability between the data obtained. However, in this article it has been written in the form of a description.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the research background, this research consists of two parts, namely 1) an assessment of the KKNi curriculum for the PBSI Unissula study program, and 2) a proposal for the KKNi curriculum for the PBSI Unissula study program. In the KKNi curriculum assessment section, there are four things, namely a) curriculum objectives, b) curriculum materials, c) curriculum methods, and d) curriculum evaluation. The proposal section for the IQF curriculum consists of a) the contents of the instrument, b) the language of the instrument, and c) the format of the instrument. The instrument for evaluating the KKNi PBSI curriculum has been compiled and validated by the validator. In this case, the validator is the Head of the PBSI Unissula Study Program at the time of preparing the KKNi curriculum, namely Mrs. Leli Nisfi Setiana, M.Pd. The selection of the validator was because at that time he was the manager of the PBSI study program who was responsible for the implementation of the PBSI curriculum. The hope is that with the validator, suggestions regarding things that need to be evaluated in the implementation of the IQF curriculum as well as curriculum problems that need to be included in the instrument. There is only one validator in this study because Mrs. Dr. Aida Azizah, M.Pd. as a member in this study. Evaluation of the KKNi curriculum for the PBSI study program is carried out by observing the curriculum that has been prepared by the PBSI Unissula study program. Observations were made by lecturers and students as users of the curriculum. The curriculum objectives in this study refer to the research of Safitri and Kisyani (2016) with adjustments, there are 13 items, namely (1) the suitability of the curriculum objectives with higher education, (2) the suitability of the curriculum objectives with the vision and mission of the Unissula PBSI Study Program, (3) the suitability of the curriculum with the needs of the community/jobs, (4) curriculum conformity with the development of Indonesian Language and Literature Education, (5) the ability of curriculum objectives to foster interest in researching in the field of Education, Indonesian Language and Literature, (6) the ability of the curriculum to develop knowledge in the field of Education, Indonesian Language and Literature, (7) the

ability of curriculum objectives to foster students' scientific attitudes, (8) the suitability of study program learning outcomes with course learning outcomes, (9) balance of special skills on study program learning outcomes, (10) specific skills on learning outcomes study program, (11) representativeness of study program achievement in courses, (12) clarity and learning outcomes of study programs in course descriptions, (13) conformity of course learning outcomes with KKNi level 6 qualifications. These thirteen points serve as guidelines in observing and evaluating the KKNi curriculum of the Unissula PBSI Study Program. Each item is given a score range of 1-4. A score of 1 means less, a score of 2 means enough, a score of 3 means good, and a score of 4 means very good. Based on these observations, it can be described as follows.

V. CURRICULUM GOALS

Question number 1, the curriculum objectives are in accordance with the goals of higher education, the lecturer score is 3.5 while the student score is 3. The second question, the curriculum objectives are in accordance with the vision and mission of the PBSI study program, the lecturer score is 3, the student score is 3.7. The third question, the curriculum objectives are in accordance with the needs of the community/employment, the lecturer score is 2.7, the student score is 3. The fourth question, the curriculum objectives are in accordance with Indonesian education, language, and literature, the lecturer score is 3.3, the student score is 3.5. The fifth question, the purpose of the curriculum is to be able to foster interest and ability to research in the fields of education, language, and Indonesian literature. Lecturer score 3, student score 3.2. The sixth question, the purpose of the curriculum is to be able to develop knowledge of education, language, and Indonesian literature. Lecturer score 2.9 student score 3.3. The seventh question, the purpose of the curriculum is to be able to foster a scientific attitude of students. Lecturer score 3, student score 3.2. The eighth question, study study achievement in accordance with subject learning achievement, lecturer score 3.3 student score 3. The ninth question, specific skills in study program learning achievement is very balanced between educational competence, language competence and literary competence. Lecturer score 3, student score 3.5. The tenth question, there are special skills to be able to speak regional languages. Lecturer score 3.2, student score 3.7. The eleventh question, the process of self-evaluation of the working group has been represented by the course. Lecturer score 2.5, student score 3. The twelfth question, study program learning achievements (covering general abilities, work field abilities, knowledge abilities, and managerial abilities) are clearly stated in the course description, lecturer scores 2.2 student scores 2.5. The thirteenth question, the learning achievement of the subject is in accordance with level 6 KKNi. Lecturer score 3, student score 3.2. The average results obtained from observations made by lecturers are 2.9. This means that the objectives of the KKNi curriculum for the PBSI study program are considered sufficient by the lecturers, in this case the lecturers as curriculum users. It is different with the

observations made by students as curriculum users. The mean obtained from observations made by students is 3.8. This means that the PBSI Study Program's KKNi curriculum objectives are considered good by students.

VI. CURRICULUM MATERIAL

Referring to the curriculum definition according to the Ministry of National Education (2009) and Safitri and Kisyani (2016), there are 10 things that are evaluated in the curriculum material, namely (1) special courses that produce achievements in the form of proficient Indonesian spoken and written, (2) balance of subjects compulsory and optional, (3) BIPA courses as elective courses, (4) preparation of courses in the curriculum structure systematically and according to student characteristics, (5) scientific attitudes represented in the courses in the curriculum structure, (6) the KKNi parameters contained in the courses in the curriculum structure, (7) the ability of the courses to encourage students to reach the IQF qualification level 6, (8) the characteristics of the study programs in the courses, (9) learning achievements in the course description, (10) exposure study, reference sources, and course objectives in the course description. These ten points serve as guidelines for observing and evaluating the KKNi curriculum of the Unissula PBSI study program. Each item is given a score range of 1-4. A score of 1 means less, a score of 2 means enough, a score of 3 means good, and a score of 4 means very good. The results of observations on curriculum materials can be described as follows. The first question is that there are courses that can specifically produce language and literature learning outcomes orally, the lecturer's score is 3.2, the student's score is 2.8. The second question, elective courses and compulsory courses are very balanced, the lecturer score is 2.7 while the student score is 3.2. The third question, there is a BIPA course as an elective course, the lecturer's score is 2.9, while the student's score is 3.7. The fourth question, the courses in the curriculum structure have been systematically arranged according to the characteristics and abilities of students, the lecturer's score is 2.7, while the student's score is 3.4. The fifth question, the courses in the curriculum structure present a scientific attitude that can be measured, the lecturer's score is 2.7, while the student's score is 3.4. The sixth question is that the courses in the curriculum structure contain KKNi parameters consisting of attitudes, general skills, special skills, and knowledge, the lecturer score is 2.9, while the student score is 3.4. The seventh question is that the courses in the curriculum structure can encourage students to reach the IQF qualification level 6, the lecturer's score is 2.9, while the student's score is 3.5. The eighth question, there are courses that can characterize the Unissula PBSI study program, including the Prophetic Literature course. The lecturer score is 2.2 while the student score is 3.2. The ninth question, there is a desired learning achievement/competence in the course description, the lecturer's score is 3.4, while the student's score is 3.6. The tenth question, there is an explanation of what will be studied and studied in the course description, the lecturer score is 3.4, while the student score is 3.4. The eleventh

question, the reference sources in the course description are presented in full and up to date, the lecturer score is 2.4, the score is 2.4. student 2.2. The twelfth question, the objectives of the courses listed in the course description are in accordance with the achievement of the IQF qualification for the undergraduate level/level 6. Lecturer score is 3.2, student score is 3.3. So it can be concluded that the mean obtained from observations made by lecturers is 2.8. This means that the KKNi curriculum material for the PBSI Unissula study program is considered sufficient by the PBSI Unissula lecturers, this is as a curriculum user. However, this is different from the observations made by students as curriculum users. The mean obtained from observations made by students is 3.3. This means that the KKNi curriculum material for the PBSI Unissula study program is considered good by students.

VII. CURRICULUM STRATEGY/METHOD

In this study, curriculum strategy is also defined as a method of implementing the curriculum in the Unissula PBSI study program. The strategy for implementing the curriculum is related to the way in which teaching, assessment, guidance, overall study program activities are arranged, the selection of teaching methods, and the selected teaching media (Safitri and Kisyani (2016). In accordance with this definition, the things evaluated in the strategy are: / Curriculum methods of KKNi PBSI Unissula Study Program, namely (1) learning methods for subjects in the curriculum, (2) practical activities with lecturer guidance, (3) student involvement in planning and implementing lectures, (4) lecture methods in course descriptions, (5) the suitability of the subject lecturers with the competencies possessed. These five things serve as a guide for researchers in observing and evaluating the curriculum strategy of the KKNi PBSI Unissula study program. Each item is given a score range of 1-4. A score of 1 means less, a score of 2 means sufficient, a score of 3 means good, and a score of 4 means very good. Based on the results of observations of the strategy/ curriculum method obtained the following results. The first question, most of the courses in the curriculum require learning methods that activate students, the lecturer scores 3.2, while the student scores 3. The second question, most of the courses in the curriculum require practical activities with the guidance of the lecturer, the lecturer scores 3.2, while student score 2.7. The third question, most of the courses in the curriculum invite students to be directly involved in planning and implementing lecture activities, the lecturer scores 2.7, while the student scores 2. The fourth question, the lecture method to be carried out is described in the course description, the lecturer score is 3, 2 while the student score is 3.5. The fifth question, the lecturers who support the courses listed in the course descriptions are in the form of teams and according to their respective competencies, the lecturer's score is 2.2, while the student's score is 2.4. Based on these results, the mean obtained from observations made by lecturers is 2.9. This means that the curriculum strategy of the KKNi PBSI Unissula Study Program is considered sufficient by the lecturers as curriculum users. The same mean score was

also obtained from observations made by students as curriculum users. This means that the KKNi curriculum strategy for the PBSI Unissula study program is considered adequate by students.

VIII. CURRICULUM ORGANIZATION

In this study, curriculum organization means the structure and implementation of the PBSI Unissula study program curriculum. Several things were observed in the curriculum organization, namely (1) the distribution of courses in the curriculum structure, (2) the preparation of teaching materials, (3) the curriculum implementation system, (4) the division of the weight of the courses in the curriculum structure. These four things serve as guidelines for observing and evaluating the organization of the KKNi curriculum for the Unissula PBSI study program. Each item is given a score range of 1-4. A score of 1 means less, a score of 2 means enough, a score of 3 means good, and a score of 4 means very good. The first question, the distribution of courses in the curriculum structure is appropriate, the score of lecturers is 3.2, while the score of students is 3.6. The second question, each course has its own teaching materials compiled by the lecturer/team, the lecturer's score is 2.2, while the student's score is 3.2. The third question, the implementation of the curriculum in semesters with face-to-face 16 times including UTS and UAS for the subject weight of 2 credits, the lecturer score is 3.7, while the student score is 3.8. The fourth question, the weight of the credits for each course is appropriate, the lecturer's score is 3.2 while the student's score is 3.2. The fifth question, the system of repeating courses by repeating in the following year (when the courses are offered), the lecturer's score is 3.7, while the student's score is 3.2. Based on these results, the mean obtained from observations made by lecturers is 3.2. This means that the curriculum organization of the KKNi PBSI Study Program is considered good by the lecturers as curriculum users. The same thing with observations made by students as curriculum users. The mean obtained from observations made by students is 3.4. This means that the KKNi curriculum organization for the PBSI Unissula study program is considered good by students.

IX. CURRICULUM EVALUATION

The evaluation of the curriculum in this study includes several things, namely (1) the use of written tests, (2) the use of performance tests, (3) evaluations in course descriptions, and (4) test validity. These four things serve as guidelines in observing and evaluating the KKNi curriculum of the Unissula PBSI study program. Each item is given a score range of 1-4. A score of 1 means less, a score of 2 means enough, a score of 3 means good, and a score of 4 means very good. Based on the results of observations of evaluations in the curriculum, it can be described as follows. In the first question, most of the courses in the curriculum require a written test as a measuring tool, the lecturer's score is 3.2, while the student's score is 3.6. In the second question, most of the courses in the curriculum require a performance test as a

measuring tool, the lecturer's score is 3.2, while the student's score is 3.4. The third question, between courses that require a written test as a measuring tool and courses that require a performance test as a measuring tool in a balanced curriculum, the lecturer's score is 2.7, while the student's score is 3.6. The fourth question, the evaluation carried out is described in the course description, the lecturer's score is 3.2, while the student's score is 3.8. The fifth question, there is validation of written test questions for UAS, the lecturer's score is 2.2, while the student's score is 3.7. Based on these observations, the average obtained from observations made by lecturers is 2.9. This means that the evaluation in the KKNi curriculum of the Unissula PBSI study program is considered sufficient by the lecturers as curriculum users. This is different from the observations made by students as curriculum users. The mean obtained from observations made by students is 3.6. This means that the evaluation of the Unissula PBSI KKN curriculum is considered good.

X. CLOSING

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that the implementation of the KKNi curriculum for the PBSI Unissula study program has been going well in all components, but improvements need to be made to improve the implementation of the next curriculum.

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